

RUBBER FORMING OF CONTINUOUS FIBRE REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITES

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ABSTRACT

In order to be able to manufacture high quality continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic (CFRTP) parts it is needed to have a good understanding of (and a feeling for) the fundamental behaviour of the material during processing. Research has been done on this topic and has been used for optimizing the "rubber forming process". The research has also resulted an automated thermoforming unit suitable for producing CFRTP parts in a fast and highly reproducible way.

Keywords : continuous fibres, interply slip, intraply shear, rubber forming, thermoforming

1. INTRODUCTION

When a continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic composite is forced in a specific form by any forming technique, the continuous fibres have to adjust to that same form. Because of the composition of CFRTP's they cannot undergo local deformations like metals can. Deformation at one spot of the material may influence the whole laminate. Therefore it is needed to know what adjustments have to be made and which process parameter settings are best to control the deformation of the fabric.

In this paper the rubber forming process for the manufacturing of continuous fibre reinforced thermoplastic composites will be briefly explained. It is basically restricted to the deformation of flat plates in to three-dimensional shapes.

First the different steps of the process will be walked through and for each step the specific processing problems are discussed. Finally some examples of products manufactured with the rubber forming process are given.

2. RUBBER FORMING PROCESS

The rubber forming process basically consists of three steps (Figure 1). First the heating phase where the viscosity of the thermoplastic resin is lowered beneath a certain level followed by the deformation phase where the composite sheet is deformed in to a three dimensional product-shape and finally the (re)consolidation phase where inhomogeneities which are introduced during the process are removed.

Figure 1 : Rubber forming process

During the rubber forming process only a few options are available to control it. In the heating phase the heating temperature, the heating time and when using contact heating the contact pressure can be set.

During the deformation phase the temperature of the composite material can be controlled by using heated moulds or mould materials which have bad heat conductivity properties. Furthermore the deformation velocity can be set and forces, needed for the deformation of the composite sheet, can be introduced .

Finally for the (re)consolidation phase the temperature can be controlled in the same way as during the deformation. A cooling system in the moulds might be added. Furthermore the consolidation time and the consolidation pressure can be varied.

A small variation in the settings of these controls can have large consequences for the final quality of the product.

Considering the limited control options it is necessary to have a complete understanding of what influence variations in the settings have on the material behaviour.

2.1 Heating

To make the deformation of the laminate possible the viscosity of the thermoplastic composite is lowered by heating it up.

Problems may occur when the material has either been heated too high or too low [1].

Too high temperatures may lead to :

- material degradation
- longer deformation cycles
- drifting of the fibres

Too low temperatures may lead to :

- internal stresses
- highly oriented polymer chains
- intolerable deformation modes

A specific heating curve may look like this:

Figure 2: General rubber forming process profile

During the pressing phase the temperature of the laminate can drop very fast. By using heated moulds some extra deformation time above the glass transition temperature can be obtained which may improve the quality of the product.

2.2 Deformation

The rubber forming process uses two matching dies (a female and a male) to press a shape in a composite sheet (Figure 3). At least one of the dies is made out of rubber.

Figure 3 : Matched-die forming principle

During the deformation phase of the process the following deformation modes may occur [2]:

Interply slip

When a flat plate is folded at high temperature the outer layers will have to travel a longer way through the corners than the inner layers. This makes slipping of the layers relative to each other necessary. The amount of slip depends on the ply thickness and the deformation angle of the material. It can be modelled by combining two extreme

cases (Figure 4).

The first type describes the situation when two areas are in contact without a resin interlayer [3]. This case can be looked upon as a situation where the fibre volume percentage is 100%. The other extreme case is when the fibre volume percentage is 0%. Now the rheological behaviour of the resin will entirely describe the slip behaviour. In a practical situation the contribution of either of the cases to the interply slip behaviour will depend on the fibre volume percentage.

Figure 4 : Interply-slip model

The temperature (\approx the viscosity) has a very distinct influence on the slip behaviour. A higher temperature ($=$ lower viscosity) eases the slipping of the layers

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Figure 5 : The reacting shear stress decreases at higher temperatures which eases the slipping

Intraply shear

For manufacturing 3-D shapes it is necessary that the fibres will shear. The maximum amount of shear depends on temperature, fabric type, time and applied stress [4] (Figure 6).

Figure 6: Influence of temperature and pressure on the maximum shearing angle of an impregnated fabric

Fabric stretching

Because of stresses during the thermoforming process the fabric may be stretched. This may affect the mechanical properties of the product. Research has indicated that the production process of the prepreg material can lead to different properties in warp and weft direction [5].

2.3 Consolidation

After the material has been deformed to its final shape this shape has to be "frozen". Inhomogeneities that have been introduced during the process have to be removed again. Therefore the viscosity of the material has to be sufficiently low and a certain amount of time has to be available to remove these inhomogeneities. By applying a high pressure during the consolidation of the material the contact between the plies that have lost contact during deformation has to be intensified. A low viscosity and thus a high consolidation temperature ease the removal of any inhomogeneities in the composite material.

Sometimes, in the case of semi crystalline resins, the cooling down rate during the consolidation phase has to be very high to avoid too high crystallinity. This may require a cooling system in one of the dies.

2.4 Controlling the deformation

Figure 8 : Composite wing-rib

As an example of how the deformation of the fabric can be controlled the manufacturing

of a wing-rib with three round dimples is used (Figure 7). The rib is built up out of ± 45 and 0-90 layers. During the deformations the layers deform in a different way and will influence each other.

To prevent any interaction between the ± 45 - and 0-90 layers they are separately influenced. In each layer there are some fibres that do not have to move during the deformation cycle. So if these fibres can be kept straight and others can freely move in to the dimples the deformation of the fabric can be controlled. To achieve this a pattern is cut in the different prepreg layers which controls the movement of the fibres (Figure 8).

Another problem with the manufacturing of this wing-rib is the pressure in the corners of the dimples. By adding some rubber to the male die the pressure can be increased and a good filling of the corners is ensured.

3. REALISATION OF AN AUTOMATED THERMOFORMING UNIT

In cooperation with the press manufacturer FONTIJNE Holland BV an automated thermoforming unit has been realised. It consists of a fast press, infrared heaters and a transport system and has the capability of making products as large as 1.00 x 1.60 m. Now it is possible to manufacture products at a rate of at least 1 per minute, depending on the heat capacity of the material. The advantage of this system is that the processing conditions are the same for every product. In this way the influence of processing parameters can be examined more accurately. Products which are manufactured on this thermofoming unit are: composite car doors, wing ribs, suitcases and more.

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